

EARTH SCIENCES

DISTRIBUTION OF THE PARTICLES OF THE FINE TAILINGS DURING THE DREDGING OF PLACER DEPOSITS

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Abstract

A technique is proposed that allows predicting the spread of light particles along the length of the dredge section, depending on the particle size, during the dredge development of placer deposits.

Keywords: dredging method of development, placer deposits, dilution of sands in the bottom.

Currently, Russia has a fairly large-scale raw material base of gold, notable for the fact that it has a high level of development [1]. The gold mining industry has been successfully developing and consistently increasing production volumes over the past 20 years [2]. However, intensive exploitation of placer deposits has led to fact that most of them are currently depleted, and existing technologies cannot solve the main problem of placer gold mining – the natural reduction and deterioration of the raw material base [3-6]. This is due the fact that many easily accessible deposits have already been worked out, there is a deterioration of mining and geological conditions [7-11].

The highest technical and economic indicators in the development of placer deposits of minerals have a dredging method, which has a number of advantages, such as high productivity, minimum cost, the possibility of implementation in difficult hydrogeological conditions. The dredging method of extraction is quite strongly dependent on the coarseness of grading of the sands being developed. The smallest fractions of spent dredge sands fall into the bottom-hole dredge zone, which leads to a decrease in equipment productivity and most importantly, to an increase in dilution [12]. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the process of distribution of various fractions falling from tail sluice into the process water along the length of dredge section.

The particles entering the section are distributed along its bottom, obeying the Gauss distribution law.

Using the method for determining the distribution of the pulp on the alluvium map proposed by A.I. Ogurtsov [13] and the results obtained using measurements, the empirical coefficients of the normal distribution function for the separation of particles in the dredging separation were obtained.

The function of the normal distribution over the relative length for the conditions of fractionation of light particles in the process water of the draining section:

$$(f)t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}}, \quad (1)$$

where t is the parameter of the normal distribution.

$$t = \frac{l_0 - (1 - 1/2 \cdot K'_0)}{\sqrt{K'_2/3 \cdot V^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where l_0 is the relative distance from the discharge site of the light fractions;

K'_0 и K'_2 is the empirical coefficients depending on the average diameter of the light particles;

V is the average speed of the process water in the drainage section, m/s.

As a result, the values of empirical coefficients were obtained K'_0 and K'_2 for the conditions of distribution of soil particles with different coarseness of grading (see Fig. 1):

$$K'_0 = -0,01502 \cdot lg^3 d_{cp} + 0,00367 \cdot lg^2 d_{cp} + 0,48413 \cdot lg d_{cp} + 0,96753; \quad (3)$$

$$K'_2 = -0,00391 \cdot lg^3 d_{cp} - 0,01787 \cdot lg^2 d_{cp} - 0,00032 \cdot lg d_{cp} + 0,0518. \quad (4)$$

The obtained models made it possible to calculate for the most common coarseness of grading encountered during the development of placer deposits. The obtained values are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Values of empirical coefficients K'_0 and K'_2		
The diameters of the particles of the rock of the lixiviation tails d_{cp} , mm	The value of K'_0	The value of K'_2
0,0025	-0,0027	0,0005
0,0075	0,0995	0,0093
0,015	0,1879	0,0167
0,03	0,2918	0,0247
0,057	0,3998	0,0321
0,087	0,4762	0,0367
0,13	0,5519	0,0408
0,205	0,6410	0,0448
0,375	0,7631	0,0490
0,75	0,9071	0,0516
2	1,1132	0,0500
4	1,2571	0,0443
7,5	1,3839	0,0352
13	1,4906	0,0239
18	1,5513	0,0155

The obtained values of empirical coefficients are used to determine the Gaussian distribution function of light particles.

Fig. 1. Graph of the dependence of empirical coefficient K'_0 u K'_2 on $lg d_{cp}$

Probability density of particle size distribution of the i - th size along the fine tailings ($V=0,5$ m/s):

$$F_i = K'_1 \cdot (\sqrt{K'_2 \cdot (3 \cdot V^2)^{-1}})^{-1} \cdot f(t), \tag{5}$$

where K'_1 is the empirical coefficient depending on the relative distance of the distribution.

The empirical coefficient was obtained based on the results of data processing, including taking into account the actual distribution of particles of fine tailings during the development of placer deposits:

$$K'_1 = 10^{(-1,48174 \cdot lg l_0 - 2,87885)}. \tag{6}$$

The values of the probability density of the distribution of particles with different average diameters along the length of the fine tailings are obtained. The values are shown in Table 2.

According to available data from placer the North-East Russia and Siberia, coarseness of grading of sands are known [14]. Knowing the values of the maximum

and minimum partial yield for each fraction of the sand size, we determine the distribution of fractions along the length the dredge section. The initial partial yield for fine-grained particles was 100 %, for coarse-grained – 68%. The values for coarse-grained and fine-grained particles are shown in Table 3.

Table 2

Probability density of fractions distribution along the length of the fine tailings

The diameter of the particles of the rock of fine tailings, mm

l_0	0,0025	0,0075	0,015	0,03	0,057	0,087	0,13	0,205	0,375	0,75	2	4	7,5	13	18
0,1	0	0	0	0	0,009	0,028	0,065	0,134	0,272	0,486	0,868	1,197	1,581	2,09	2,598
0,2	0	0	0	0	0,004	0,009	0,018	0,03	0,052	0,081	0,127	0,164	0,208	0,273	0,35
0,3	0	0	0	0,001	0,003	0,007	0,01	0,016	0,023	0,031	0,042	0,05	0,059	0,069	0,077
0,4	0	0	0	0,001	0,004	0,006	0,008	0,01	0,013	0,016	0,018	0,02	0,02	0,019	0,016
0,5	0	0	0	0,002	0,004	0,005	0,006	0,007	0,008	0,008	0,008	0,008	0,007	0,005	0,002
0,6	0	0	0,001	0,002	0,004	0,004	0,004	0,005	0,005	0,004	0,004	0,003	0,002	0,001	0
0,7	0	0,001	0,002	0,003	0,003	0,003	0,003	0,003	0,003	0,002	0,002	0,001	0,001	0	0
0,8	0	0,002	0,002	0,002	0,002	0,002	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0	0	0	0
0,9	0	0,002	0,002	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	0,008	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3

Fractionation of fractions (partial yield in %) along the length of the fine tailings during the development of coarse-(fine) granular sands

The diameter of the particles of the rock of the fine tailings, mm

l_0	Initial partial yield is fine tailings, %														
	0,0025	0,0075	0,015	0,03	0,057	0,087	0,13	0,205	0,375	0,75	2	4	7,5	13	18
0,1	4,4(32,5)	3,7(10,1)	3,1(20,4)	2,8(25,8)	2,5(4,2)	1(3)	2,5(1)	3(0,5)	0(0)	0,1(0,93)	0,63(1,06)	0,43(1,28)	1,38(0,55)	1,93(0,32)	
0,2	0(0)	0(0)	0(0,01)	0,08(0,74)	0,27(0,46)	0,14(0,42)	0,37(0,15)	0,44(0,07)	0(0)	0,13(1,17)	0,25(0,41)	0,1(0,3)	0,22(0,09)	0,23(0,04)	
0,3	0(0)	0(0)	0,01(0,05)	0,04(0,23)	0,22(2,03)	0,09(0,26)	0,17(0,07)	0,15(0,02)	0(0)	0,13(0,85)	0,28(0,47)	0,08(0,23)	0,13(0,05)	0,1(0,02)	
0,4	0(0)	0(0)	0,13(0,85)	0,35(3,23)	0,27(0,45)	0,06(0,19)	0,1(0,04)	0,07(0,01)	0(0)	0,34(2,26)	0,48(4,38)	0,27(0,45)	0,1(0,04)	0,1(0,02)	
0,5	0(0)	0,04(0,12)	0,64(4,23)	0,52(4,82)	0,23(0,38)	0,05(0,14)	0,06(0,03)	0,04(0,01)	0(0)	0,3(0,81)	0,45(4,19)	0,23(0,38)	0,06(0,03)	0,04(0,01)	
0,6	0(0)	0,3(0,81)	0,82(5,42)	0,45(4,19)	0,16(0,27)	0,03(0,09)	0,04(0,2)	0,02(0)	0(0)	0,94(2,58)	0,16(0,27)	0,16(0,27)	0,04(0,2)	0,02(0)	
0,7	0(0)	1,42(3,87)	0,71(4,67)	0,31(2,84)	0,1(0,16)	0,02(0,01)	0,02(0,01)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0,41(2,67)	0,31(2,84)	0,02(0,01)	0,02(0,01)	0,01(0)	
0,8	0(0,03)	0,99(2,71)	0,41(2,67)	0,16(1,48)	0,05(0,08)	0,01(0)	0,01(0)	0,01(0)	0(0)						
0,9	4,4(32,47)														

Continuation of table 3

The diameter of the particles of the rock of the fine tailings, mm

l_0	Initial partial yield is fine tailings, %														
	0,375	0,75	2	4	7,5	13	18	2(0,4) <th>1,71(0,34) <th>0,89(0,02) <th>0,23(0,05) <th>0,05(0,01) <th>0,01(0) <th>0(0) <th>0(0) </th></th></th></th></th></th></th>	1,71(0,34) <th>0,89(0,02) <th>0,23(0,05) <th>0,05(0,01) <th>0,01(0) <th>0(0) <th>0(0) </th></th></th></th></th></th>	0,89(0,02) <th>0,23(0,05) <th>0,05(0,01) <th>0,01(0) <th>0(0) <th>0(0) </th></th></th></th></th>	0,23(0,05) <th>0,05(0,01) <th>0,01(0) <th>0(0) <th>0(0) </th></th></th></th>	0,05(0,01) <th>0,01(0) <th>0(0) <th>0(0) </th></th></th>	0,01(0) <th>0(0) <th>0(0) </th></th>	0(0) <th>0(0) </th>	0(0)
0,1	8(0,5)	4(1)	7(0)	5(0,2)	11(0,2)	8(0,2)	2(0,4)	8(0,2)	6,8(0,17)	1,71(0,34)	0,89(0,02)	0,23(0,05)	0,05(0,01)	0,01(0)	0(0)
0,2	5,76(0,36)	3,08(0,77)	5,68(0)	4,15(0,17)	9,26(0,17)	6,8(0,17)	1,71(0,34)	6,8(0,17)	9,26(0,17)	1,71(0,34)	0,89(0,02)	0,23(0,05)	0,05(0,01)	0,01(0)	0(0)
0,3	1,11(0,07)	0,52(0,13)	0,83(0)	0,57(0,02)	1,22(0,02)	0,89(0,02)	0,23(0,05)	0,89(0,02)	1,22(0,02)	0,23(0,05)	0,05(0,01)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
0,4	0,49(0,03)	0,2(0,05)	0,28(0)	0,17(0,01)	0,35(0,01)	0,23(0,01)	0,05(0,01)	0,23(0,01)	0,35(0,01)	0,05(0,01)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
0,5	0,28(0,02)	0,1(0,02)	0,12(0)	0,07(0)	0,12(0)	0,06(0)	0,01(0)	0,06(0)	0,12(0)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
0,6	0,17(0,01)	0,05(0,01)	0,06(0)	0,03(0)	0,04(0)	0,02(0)	0(0)	0,04(0)	0,04(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
0,7	0,1(0,01)	0,03(0,01)	0,03(0)	0,01(0)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0,01(0)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
0,8	0,06(0)	0,01(0)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
0,9	0,03(0)	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
1	0,01(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)

According to the data obtained, it can be concluded that with an increase in the average diameter, the distance traveled by the particle relative to the dumping

site decreases. Small particles, on the contrary, overcome a long distance. An example of the distribution is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2

Change in the weighted average diameter of the fine tailing fractions along the length of the dredge section

The dependences of the average diameter of the fine particles on the distance of the tailing propagation were revealed.

For coarse-grained particles:

$$d_{c.B} = 23,214 \cdot e^{-7,847l_0}. \quad (7)$$

For fine-grained particles:

$$d_{c.B} = 0,0092 \cdot l_0^{-2,456}. \quad (8)$$

Thus, the presented technique makes it possible to predict the distribution of fine particles according to the signs of a dredging section, depending on the size. Understanding the distribution of the process includes the ability to build a longitudinal profile at the development and design stage. This knowledge is necessary to clarify the dilution of sands in the bottom hole zone for monitoring the fine tailings and developing its indicators based on measures.

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